

A New and Convenient Synthesis of 2:4-Dihydroxybenzophenone.

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It has been known that dialkylaminobenzophenones can be prepared by the condensation of benzanilides with dialkylanilines in the presence of phosphorus oxychloride (D.R.P. 41751; Friedlander, I, 44,47; Meisenheimer, Budkewicz and Kananow, *Annalen*, 1921, 423, 75; Shah, Deshpande and Chaubal, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 642). The authors attempted a similar condensation under various conditions, using resorcinol in place of a dialkylaniline, but no condensation took place and benzanilide was more or less completely recovered unchanged. However, with a mixture of fused zinc chloride and phosphorus oxychloride as a condensing agent, the expected condensation readily took place with a 30% yield of 2:4-dihydroxybenzophenone, though zinc chloride alone was ineffective. The condensation proceeded still better when benzanilide was replaced by benzamide, the yield being 35%. The probable course of the reaction is as follows, the intermediate product being a ketimide as in the Höesch synthesis:

(R = Ph in the case of benzanilide; R = H in the case of benzamide).

In the experiment with benzamide, a neutral oil was also obtained and this was identified as benzonitrile, which must have been formed by the dehydrating action of phosphorus oxychloride on a part of the benzamide. A mixture of benzamide and phosphorus oxychloride at 100° gave an almost quantitative yield of benzonitrile. This observation was extended to some other amides also, but as we have been anticipated in this respect by Von Braun and Rudolph (*Ber.*, 1934, 67,

1762), who have made a similar observation, an account of these experiments is not included.

As a matter of independent interest, several other possible methods for the preparation of 2:4-dihydroxybenzophenone were also investigated.

The known method in which benzoic acid is heated with resorcinol in the presence of zinc chloride (Komarowsky and Kostanecki, *Ber.*, 1894, 27, 1997) is of no preparative value, as the yield was only 2.1 g. from 20 g. of resorcinol. Attempted condensation of benzoic acid and resorcinol with concentrated sulphuric acid or phosphorus oxychloride was unsuccessful. Condensation with the help of stannic chloride gave in one experiment a 49% yield, but the experiment could not be repeated and subsequent experiments gave very low yields. Condensation in benzene with phosphoric anhydride gave resorcinol monobenzoate, resorcinol dibenzoate and 2:4-dihydroxybenzophenone (poor yield). Benzanilide did not condense with resorcinol in the presence of phosphoric anhydride.

EXPERIMENTAL.

A mixture of benzanilide (10 g.), resorcinol (6 g.) and phosphorus oxychloride (20 c.c.) was heated in various experiments at temperatures ranging from 120° to 170° for 1 hour. The pasty mass was treated with ice-cold water, and the insoluble residue was boiled with 2N-NaOH for 1/2 hour. The filtered alkaline solution yielded nothing on acidification, and the product insoluble in alkali was found to be benzanilide (8.9 g.).

Condensation of Benzanilide with Resorcinol.—Benzanilide (10 g.) and resorcinol (6 g.) were mixed together and freshly fused powdered zinc chloride (10.5 g.) added, followed by phosphorus oxychloride (20 c.c.). The mixture was heated in an oil-bath at 130°-140°, until hydrogen chloride ceased to be evolved (1 hr.). After cooling, ice-water was added, and the insoluble residue boiled with excess of 2N-NaOH for 1/2 hour and filtered to remove unchanged benzanilide. Acidification of the filtrate gave a dirty greyish semisolid mass, which crystallised from much hot water in greyish needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen of 2:4-dihydroxybenzophenone prepared from resorcinol by the

Höesch reaction, m.p. 144-45°, yield 3 g. It dissolved in dilute alkali and gave a dark violet colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. The identity was further confirmed by the preparation of the dibenzoyl derivative, m.p. 140-41°; Döbner (*Annalen*, 1881, 210, 258) gives m.p. 141°.

Condensation of Benzamide with Resorcinol.—A mixture of benzamide (10 g.), resorcinol (9 g.), fused zinc chloride (11.2 g.) and phosphorus oxychloride (20 c.c.) was heated in an oil-bath. At about 100° the evolution of hydrogen chloride began. The temperature was gradually raised to 140° in the course of one hour by which time the evolution of hydrogen chloride became negligible. Water was added to the cooled melt and the mixture was heated at 100° and filtered hot to remove unreacted benzamide. The insoluble semicrystalline mass was boiled with 2*N*-NaOH for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. After cooling, the oil which had separated was extracted with ether. The residue from the ether extract was a colourless oil, b.p. 187-89°, and was identified as benzonitrile. The alkaline solution on acidification with concentrated HCl, deposited brownish needles of 2:4-dihydroxybenzophenone, which crystallised from hot water in colourless needles, m.p. 144-45°. A mixed m.p. with the product obtained from the previous experiment and with an authentic specimen showed no depression, yield 3.5-4.0 g.

Condensation of Benzoic Acid and Resorcinol.—(i) The mixture of resorcinol (20 g.), zinc chloride (30 g.) and benzoic acid (30 g.) was heated at 160° for 13 minutes. The cooled melt was washed with cold water and then with saturated NaHCO₃ solution. The residue on crystallisation from hot water gave colourless needles of 2:4-dihydroxybenzophenone (2.1 g.).

(ii) *With stannic chloride.*—Benzoic acid (30 g.) and anhydrous stannic chloride (30 g.) were heated together until a homogeneous liquid was formed. Resorcinol (20 g.) was then added and the mixture heated at 140-150° for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The mixture when cold was washed successively with water, concentrated hydrochloric acid and saturated NaHCO₃ solution. The residue on crystallisation from hot water melted at 119-130° and was found to be a mixture of two substances. Separation was effected by hot petroleum ether (b.p. 65-95°), which on cooling deposited colourless prismatic needles (m.p. 113°), probably monobenzoyl derivative of 2:4-dihydroxybenzophenone. (Found: C, 75.1; H, 4.7. C₂₀H₁₄O₄ requires C, 75.5; H, 4.4 per

cent). The compound insoluble in petroleum ether was found to be 2:4-dihydroxybenzophenone. A further quantity of the ketone was obtained from the compound, m.p. 113° , by boiling in NaOH solution for $\frac{1}{4}$ hour and subsequent acidification with concentrated HCl. The total yield of the ketone was 12.0 g. in one experiment but the experiment could not be repeated, yields in subsequent experiments being very poor.

(iii) *With phosphoric anhydride.*—Benzoic acid (20 g.), resorcinol (24 g.) and phosphoric anhydride (25 g.) in benzene (80 c.c.) were heated together in an oil-bath (120° - 130°) for 15 minutes. The benzene layer was washed with saturated NaHCO_3 solution and then extracted with sodium hydroxide solution. The alkaline extract on acidification gave a solid, which on crystallisation from alcohol melted at 136° , and was proved to be resorcinol monobenzoate by direct comparison with an authentic specimen. The residue from benzene layer was a solid which melted at 119° , after crystallisation from alcohol and was found to be resorcinol dibenzoate. The solid remaining after decanting off the benzene solution was treated with ice and then with saturated NaHCO_3 solution. The insoluble residue crystallised from hot water in needles, m.p. 144 - 45° , and was found to be 2:4-dihydroxybenzophenone. The yield was poor.

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